

INNOVATIONS IN MODERN BUILDING MATERIALS

Almasova Gulruh Iskandar qizi

Samarkand State Architecture and Construction
University named after Mirzo Ulugbek (SamSACU)
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ABSTRACT:

Modern construction materials are manufactured at the latest stage and they take the construction industry to a new level. Innovations help to improve the quality of material materials, as well as environmental cleanliness, energy efficiency and the efficiency of the construction process. modern building materials for the main innovative directions:

Keywords:

Modern building materials, self-healing concrete, fiberglass concrete, 3D printer, energy efficient, light, recycled.

Self-healing concrete (self-healing concrete) is a material that can independently repair microcracks in concrete. This innovation is connected with the direct addition of special microorganisms or encapsulated concrete. It activates when a crack forms and forms a crack-sealing material. It is a technology to improve the life and fix the repair.

Advantages: Less maintenance and repair work, Longer durability of concrete, Suitable for travel on infrastructure facilities such as bridges, tunnels and roads.

Glass fiber concrete (GFRC - Glass fiber reinforced concrete). Glass-to-reinforced concrete stands strong with its high strength and light weight. This material is due to the formation of concrete and glass fibers, as a result of which the strength of concrete increases to a high degree. Fiberglass helps to resist the absorption and cracking of concrete.

Advantages: Ease of support and installation, High strength, Restore strength and stability in structures, Wide hand control in decoration and architecture.

3D printed building materials. One thing that can be done is to set up production with 3D printers. This technology is printing through houses, bridges and various other special concrete mixtures. Materials are reliable straight from the printer and layer by layer.

Advantages: Acceleration of the construction process, Material consumption, Reduces the cost of construction of buildings, Loaded with recycled materials.

Phase change materials (PCM - Phase Change Materials). It has the storage and storage of phase-changing materials, helping to manage the

building's interior microclimate. PCM changes phase (eg from solid to damaged) when the material changes its temperature, and this process causes heat generation. Three technologies are efficient means of energy in hot climates.

Advantages: Saves energy and manages heat inside the building, Excess energy consumption in cold and hot periods, Easy to install and can be added to many different materials (plaster, concrete).

Airgels. Airgel is one of the lightest and best insulating materials, it is a solid material filled with gases. Three materials are used in construction for thermal insulation and acoustic insulation. Aerogels are very light and create a perfect balance of air and temperature.

Advantages: High level of thermal insulation. Light weight, Wide range of applications (medicine, space technology, construction).

Environmentally friendly building materials. Recycled and natural materials are taking an important place in modern construction. These innovations include the widespread use of building materials from wood, recycled plastics, and other waste materials. It contributes greatly to such materials and helps to use them.

Advantages: Saves waste, Energy and environmental protection, Provides transportation from sustainable and renewable resources.

Nanomaterials. Nanotechnologies are being incorporated into building materials, which help to improve the microstructure and quality of the materials. For example, nanoconcretes are superior to conventional concretes in terms of strength and development, and are highly resistant to corrosion and expansion.

Advantages: The strength and usefulness of concrete increases, high resistance to corrosion and growth. It can be used for the most delicate structures.

CONCLUSION

The building material is giving great importance to freedom and modern energy. Innovative solutions such as self-healing concrete, 3D printing, phase change materials and aerogels make the construction process faster, cheaper and more efficient. Along with innovation, new perspectives are emerging in the construction industry

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